

THE ROLE OF FOLKLORE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Annotation

The article's concept is still extremely important today since moral instruction through folklore produces positive and useful outcomes. Folk art, which has its roots in ancient Greece, enhances communication and helps people think figuratively. Thus, it follows logically that folklore plays a central part in an individual's moral and aesthetic upbringing. An educational resource is folklore.

Keywords: folklore, tradition, custom, writing, fairy tale, joke

A child's preschool years are crucial for the development of their personality. It is crucial that moral principles and human values are instilled in children from an early age. Children can learn valuable moral lessons from folklore. He shows and explains to the young kid the fundamentals of human interactions and the nature of existence. It enhances the child's intellect, creativity, and emotional development. To optimize the educational impact of folk art, it is crucial that it be portrayed in a range of genres and integrated into every kindergartener's conceivable activity.

The growth of innovative thinking is facilitated by folklore, which also enhances children's vocabulary and overall speech development. Children who are exposed to folklore grow to sense moral and patriotic sentiments, which are particularly significant in the development of a child's personality. Education that is moral and patriotic helps children develop a feeling of self and a sense of identity as Uzbeks. The youngster develops a sense of pride in his nation and its history as well as an identity as a Russian, thanks to Russian culture, folk traditions, customs, and

language, the child identifies himself as a Russian person, and a sense of pride in his country and its history is formed in him.

Acquaintance with folklore arouses keen interest in children, brings them a sense of joy, creates a good mood, relieves feelings of fear, anxiety, and provides emotional and psychological well-being.

Folk songs, nursery rhymes, lullabies are created on the material that is well known to children from the first days of life, close to their worldview. A huge educational potential is inherent in Russian folk tales, rituals, round dances, dances.

For several years of working as a teacher, I have constantly used various folklore genres in my work with children. I consider this not only a necessary, but also a very interesting part of the work. Having experience working with children of different ages, including those with severe speech disorders, I can note that the material embedded in Russian folk art is very interesting and close to children. I start my work with small folklore forms, staging them using different types of theater. Folklore can also be used to solve various educational tasks, for example, to discuss the topic of fire safety, staging a nursery rhyme "Cat's House".

In 2022, a children's creativity contest «Entertainers" was held in the Karshi district, in which we took part with pleasure. The folklore collective "Entertainers" was created with children of senior preschool age together with the musical director. Russian folk songs, folk games, jokes, round dance games, Russian folk dances were included in the repertoire of the band. The band performed effectively in the competition, and then, feeling strong, took part in various music competitions in the Karshi district, taking prizes. The students of the band performed with great desire and artistry. The comic text of folk songs and games caused genuine delight of the little artists, which was invariably passed on to the audience. Each appearance on stage was a long-awaited joyful event for them and caused a flurry of positive emotions.

The children willingly and fervently played Russian folk games on walks and in free group activities. New and interesting forms of work with children and their parents arose, for example, a folklore festival dedicated to Mother's Day "Gatherings with Mothers"; a performance using folklore games, songs and round dances based on the Russian folk tale "Geese-Swans".

In the near future, I plan to introduce children to a rag doll or a roll-up doll. This is an ancient doll that from time immemorial mothers in Russia made for their babies by simply twisting the fabric. There are many types of these dolls, and each has its own purpose. Watching the monster toys (hagi-wagi, kishi-misi) that modern children play with, I would like to note that they do not carry any positive educational potential and negatively affect the psyche of children. In this regard, I really want to draw the attention of children and their parents to Russian national toys, try to reveal their educational potential and beneficial effect on the psycho-emotional state of children. Making a roll-up doll together with parents and then playing it will have a positive impact on the relationship between parents and children.

Thus, the systematic use of various genres of folk art by parents and educators will necessarily have a huge impact on the harmonious development of the child's personality.

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